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Comprehensive Evaluation of Physiochemical, Nutritional and Quality Characteristics of Milk from Pakistani Dairy Goats under Different Feeding Regimes

Muhammad Yaser (Corresponding Author)

Para Veterinary Institute, University of Veterinary & Animal Sciences Layyah Campus, Karor Lal Eason, Pakistan

yaser.khan@uvas.edu.pk

Absar Ahmad

Para Veterinary Institute, University of Veterinary & Animal Sciences Layyah Campus, Karor Lal Eason, Pakistan

Qurat ul Ain

Para Veterinary Institute, University of Veterinary & Animal Sciences Layyah Campus, Karor Lal Eason, Pakistan

Tariq Nadeem

Para Veterinary Institute, University of Veterinary & Animal Sciences Layyah Campus, Karor Lal Eason, Pakistan

Maha Maqsood

University of Education, Bank Road Campus, Lahore, Pakistan

Nadeem Raza

Para Veterinary Institute, University of Veterinary & Animal Sciences Layyah Campus, Karor Lal Eason, Pakistan

Zia ur Rahman Farooqi

Para Veterinary Institute, University of Veterinary & Animal Sciences Layyah Campus, Karor Lal Eason, Pakistan

Sabah Mansoor

Department of Allied Sciences, University of Home Economics, Lahore, Pakistan

Muhammad Rizwan

Multan College of Veterinary Sciences, Multan University of Science and Technology, Multan Pakistan

Abdul Aziz

Department of Veterinary Clinical Sciences, Faculty of Veterinary and Animal Sciences, University of Poonch Rawalakot, Azad Kashmir, Pakistan

ABSTRACT

A comparative study was conducted to assess the effects of fodder and concentrate feeding on milk production and physico-chemical characteristics of two indigenous Pakistani dairy goat breeds, Beetal and Dera Din Panah (DDP). Twenty goats from each breed were randomly selected for feeding trials. Milk samples were analyzed using the Generalized Linear Model procedure in SAS 9.1. Results showed that concentrate supplementation significantly ($P < 0.05$) increased milk yield, lactation length, milk fat, total solids (TS), solids-not-fat (SNF), and body weight in both breeds. Beetal goats produced higher milk yield (0.964 L/day) and longer lactation length (128.2

days) than DDP goats (0.832 L/day and 125.6 days, respectively). Specific gravity was not significantly affected ($P>0.05$) by feeding regime or breed. Overall, concentrate feeding improved milk quality and production traits, while Beetal goats demonstrated superior performance compared to DDP goats. These findings suggest that concentrate supplementation can enhance dairy goat productivity under Pakistani farming conditions.

Key Words; Dairy goats, Beetal, Dera Din Panah (DDP), concentrate feeding, fodder feeding, milk yield

Introduction

Goat is considered as one of the smallest ruminants which are domesticated in the world. Pakistan has about 30 local goat breeds (Afzal and Naqvi., 2004). Due to nominal feeding of goats and adoptability of this species for among landless poor people, it is considered as “poor man’s cow” (Abdullah., 2024). Beetal and Dera Din Panah (DDP) goats are one of the important milk and meat breeds in the Central Punjab including Muzaffargarh, Layyah and Multan Districts of Punjab Province in Pakistan (Khan *et al.*, 2005). The remarkable numbers of goats (90%) are present in developing countries as compared to developed world. Asia leads the rest of the continents by producing 80% of goat milk. India, China, Bangladesh, Iran, Pakistan & Turkey are the main countries that produce goat milk (Khan *et al.*, 2003).

Goat milk in comparison to cow’s milk is considered as naturally homogenized and it has higher level of medium chain fatty acids which makes it easier to digest and rarely causes lactose intolerance. The major producer of goat milk in the world is India (22%), and in Europe: Greece (4.2%) then France (4.1%). Biggest goat cheese exporters are France, Italy, Spain, Switzerland, Greece & Cyprus (Bernacka., 2009). The rearing of animals on low productive marginal lands is insufficient to fulfil the needs of increasing human population. The feed supply balance sheet showed a deficient level of feeding pool of livestock is given as (21 %), energy (29 %) and crude protein (33 %) availability of dry matter. The animals, during routine feeding are receiving only seventy five percent of the required quantity of DE (Digestible Energy) while the percentage of digestible crude protein is only 40 % (Sekaran *et al.*, 2021).

To uplift & flourish the farming of livestock in the world, the national level and international level research and development approaches are necessary for the economic empowerment of the developing countries. There is a dire need to improve and access more elaborative research outputs and results through developing and enhancing research and extension services that should assist the goat industries of developing countries. The demands are continuously increasing due to increase in human population in these countries (Boyazoglu *et al.*, 2005). The milk of several European goat breeds has lower fat contents in the tropics as compared to production temperate zones. Goat milk contains higher level of calcium and chloride but less N-acetyl neuromeric acid, orotic acid, folate, vitamin B₁₂ & vitamin B₆ than the cow milk (Iqbal, *et al.*, 2008).

The addition corn silage or rich in concentrate diets along with vegetable oils in the diets of dairy goats surely increases trans fatty acids other than rumenic and vaccenic acids (Sampelayo *et al.*, 2007). There is a limited research work on various aspects of milk production and composition of dairy goats in Pakistan. In spite of the importance of feeding management strategies & milk production, there are inadequate information’s and researches on the evaluation of concentrate rations in combination with conventional feeding and its’ effects on milk production on Beetal goats in Pakistan.

Materials and Methods

Out of 123 DDP and 232 Beetal goats, 50 goats of each breed, meeting specific criteria were included in the study and later 20 goats of each breed were randomly selected for feeding trials for a month. Two feeding trials i.e. Conventional Feeding (Fodder) and Energy Rich Diet (Concentrate) were treated on 10 dairy goats of each breed. The animals kept at conventional feeding were offered routine grazing while other animals of both breeds were additionally offered energy rich ration @ 5% of their body weight throughout the month. A local made concentrate ration having CP-17.41%, DM-83.26% and TDN-71% was offered to these goats. The Milk samples of all goats under different feedings were collected on weekly basis for a whole month on regular intervals i.e. 0, 7, 14, 21 & 28th day. Once time whole milking was done without suckling and kids were fed manually through feeders. The samples were regularly sent to Milk Testing Laboratory, University of Veterinary & Animal Sciences, Lahore (Pakistan) for analysis of Fat, SNF, TS and Specific gravity, according to the procedure described by (Khan *et al.*, 2005).

Determination of Fat %age

Gerber's method was adopted for the estimation of fat content in milk. With this method the milk fat is separated from milk by strongly acidifying and centrifuging the milk in an acid-butyrometer. In this method, the casein of milk is dissolved by means of 90% sulphuric acid and separation of fat is facilitated by the addition of amyl alcohol. This prevents partial charring of fat and sugar by the sulphuric acid, keeps the fat clear and renders separation of fat easier.

Determination of Total Solids & Solids Not Fat

The specific gravity of milk was calculated through lactometer readings while total solids and SNF were calculated by the following formulas:

$$\text{Percentage of total solids} = \text{CLR}/4 + 1.2 \times F$$

$$\text{Percentage of Solids Not Fat} = \text{CLR}/4 + 0.2 \times F$$

Where,

CLR = Lactometer (Quevenne) reading corrected to 60F°

F= Percentage of Fat

The data was analyzed with SPSS (Statistical Package for Social Sciences) version 20 and SAS version 9.1. The comparative differences or similarities related to milk production and composition among the Breed and Treatment groups were calculated with GLM procedure which was based on ANOVA, Mix Model Procedure, LSD and Duncan's Multiple Range Test.

Results and Discussion

Average Milk Yield (Liters)

The average milk yield (liters) was significantly affected ($P < 0.05$) due to changing feeding sources i.e. fodder and concentrates. The milk yield was seen increased due to offering concentrate ($P < 0.0001$). No significant effect of Breed x Treatment on the average milk yield of goat breeds was observed. The mean value of Average Milk Production of Beetal and DDP goats was 0.847 and 0.763, respectively while the average milk yield (liters) of both breeds on fodder and concentrate rations was 0.729 (B-F), 0.964(B-C), 0.693(D-F) and 0.832(D-C), **Table 1**.

Statistical analysis showed highly significant difference ($P < 0.0001$) between treatments. Similar results were found by two other research groups and them and reported improved milk production by 20-25% with the increase in level of concentrate (Min *et al.*, 2005). The results of this study are in agreement with Sampelayo and his co-workers (Sampelayo *et al.*, 2000), who also reported higher milk production ($P < 0.05$) in goats with concentrate supplementation. The

results are also in agreement with Greling (Greyling *et al.*, 2004) who found that the Boar goat and indigenous does produced more ($P < 0.05$) milk under the intensive systems, compared to the extensive nutritional regime.

Lactation Length (Days)

The mean lactation length (days) of Beetal and DDP goats on different Treatments were 18.9 (B-F), 128.2(B-C), 117.1(D-F) and 125.6(D-C). There was significant difference ($P < 0.05$) of Lactation Length among breeds. The results are in close agreement with Kramarenko *et al.*, 2025, who also evaluated lactation length from 34 herds (231 ± 1 days). Milk yield and lactation length were primarily influenced by Concentrate x Fodder.

Specific Gravity

Specific gravity of milk was not affected ($P > 0.05$) due to change in feeding source. There was no significant effect in Breeds, Treatments and Breed x Treatment ($P > 0.05$) on the specific gravity of milk. The average mean value of Specific Gravity of Beetal and DDP (Table 1) was 1.034 and 1.026, respectively while the results of Specific Gravity on different treatments were 1.042(B-F), 1.026(B-C), 1.025(D-F) and 1.027(D-C). The range of specific gravity in various goat breeds was determined by research group (Asif and Sumaira., 2010) in their research finding which supports the conclusions of present study.

Fat %age

Fat %age of milk was significantly affected ($P < 0.05$) due to change in feeding source i.e. fodder and concentrate. However, there was no significant difference among breeds ($P > 0.05$) but there was highly significant difference in Treatments ($P < 0.0001$) while Breed x Treatment difference was also significant ($P < 0.0006$). The average mean value of Fat %age in Beetal and DDP goats (Table 1) was 3.10 and 3.14, respectively while the results of Fat %age on different treatments were 2.86(B-F), 3.35(B-C), 2.51(D-F) and 3.76(D-C). It was concluded that fat contents are present in the range of 3.16% to 4.73% in goat milk samples which are in agreement of the present study (Asif and Sumaira., 2010). When researchers fed goats (Alpine x Beetal) on three diets different in CP% and reported that the fat contents of milk were increased significantly having % ages of 3.77, 3.44 and 3.89 in groups A, B and C, respectively. Sampelayo and his co-workers also reported that the concentrate supplemented goats showed higher ($P < 0.05$) milk fat contents (Sampelayo *et al.*, 2000),

Total Solids

Total Solids (TS) %age of milk was significantly affected ($P < 0.05$) due to changing feeding sources i.e. fodder and concentrate. However, there was no significant difference among breeds ($P > 0.05$) but there was highly significant difference within Treatments ($P < 0.0001$) while Breed x Treatment difference was also significant ($P < 0.05$). The average mean value of Total Solids in Beetal and DDP goat milk (Table 1) was 10.86 and 11.15, respectively while the findings of Total Solids on various Treatments were 10.40 (B-F), 11.33(B-C), 10.15(D-F) and 12.17(D-C). The results are in close agreement with other scientists (Min *et al.*, 2005), who studied the effect of diets on milk production and composition in pastured dairy goats. In accordance to their study, dairy goats supplemented with 0.66 kg, 0.33 kg or 0 kg of concentrate rations per kg of milk over 1.5kg/day surely affected milk production and composition in comparison to pastured grazing and on fodder. Goats supplemented with 0.66 kg concentrate led to greater TS %age as compared to other treatments.

Solids not Fat (SNF)

SNF %age of milk was significantly affected ($P < 0.05$) due to change in feed source i.e. fodder and concentrate. However, there was also significant difference among Breeds ($P < 0.05$) but there was highly significant difference within Treatments ($P < 0.0001$) and Breed x Treatment difference was non-significant. The mean values of SNF %age in Beetal and DDP breeds (Table 1) were 10.87 and 11.16, respectively while the percentage of SNF %age under different Treatments were 7.55(B-F), 7.98(B-C), 7.63(D-F) & 8.40(D-C). The results are in close agreement with Shetaawi and his colleagues who reported significant difference ($P < 0.05$) in milk SNF contents in adult Damascus goats fed with concentrate diets (Shetaawi *et al.*, (2001).

Table 1. Milk Parameters of dairy goat breeds fed on Fodder or Concentrate diets											
Parameters	Main effects				Simple Effects				P-Values		
	Breed		Treatment		Beetal		DDP		F 1	F 2	F 1 * F 2
	Beetal	DDP	Fodder	Conc.	Fodder (B-F)	Conc. (B-C)	Fodder (D-F)	Conc. (D-C)			
Aveg. Milk Production (liters)	0.84 ^{7a}	0.76 ^{3b}	0.71 ^{1b}	0.898 ^a	0.72 ⁹	0.9 ⁶	0.69 ³	0.8 ³²	0.00 ⁶	<.00 ⁰¹	0.10 ⁶⁹
Specific Gravity (Milk)	1.03 ^{4a}	1.02 ^{6a}	1.03 ^{4a}	1.027 ^a	1.04 ²	1.0 ³	1.02 ⁵	1.0 ³	0.38 ¹³	0.42 ⁴²	0.30 ⁴¹
Milk Fat %	3.10 ^a	3.14 ^a	2.68 ^b	3.5 ^{5a}	2.86 ⁵	3.3 ⁵	2.51 ⁶	3.7 ⁶	0.73 ⁹⁹	<.00 ⁰¹	0.00 ⁰⁶
Total Solids % (Milk)	10.8 ^{7a}	11.1 ^{6a}	10.2 ^{8b}	11.75 ^a	10.4 ⁰	11. ³	10.1 ⁵	12. ²	0.10 ⁹⁶	<.00 ⁰¹	0.00 ³⁴
Solid Not Fat % (milk)	7.77 ^a	7.01 ^a	7.59 ^b	8.2 ^{0a}	7.55 ⁸	7.9 ⁸	7.63 ⁰	8.4 ⁰	0.19 ²²	<.00 ⁰¹	0.10 ⁷⁹
F 1: Breeds											
F 2: Treatments											
F1*F2: Interaction of Breeds & Treatments											
Means within rows sharing common superscript small letter are not significantly different ($P > 0.05$) and vice versa											
Graph 1. Comparison of milk production in different breeds with different feeds											

Conclusion

This study evaluated the effects of diet (concentrate vs. fodder) on the milk yield, lactation length, and milk composition of Beetal and DDP dairy goat breeds. Offering a concentrate ration significantly increased average milk yield and prolonged lactation length, with Beetal goats fed concentrates achieving the highest overall yield and longest lactation, compared to a study-low among fodder-fed DDP goats. Conversely, milk composition peaked in the **DDP** breed fed

concentrates, which yielded the highest Fat, Total Solids, and SNF, while diet and breed had no significant effect on specific gravity. Ultimately, while DDP goats produced richer milk on concentrates, Beetal goats demonstrated superior overall performance due to their longer lactation period. The study concludes that fodder and concentrate should be offered simultaneously to maximize both milk volume and quality, and recommends further research to identify optimum concentrate levels for native dairy goats.

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